

Competitive Intelligence and Entrepreneurship Skills as Correlates in Marketing Library Services among Academic Librarians in Lagos State Public Universities in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigates entrepreneurship skills and competitive intelligence as correlates of marketing library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities, Nigeria. The library has modernised its services by engaging entrepreneurship skills in order to promote service delivery that will be effective in this technological era. The study adopts a descriptive research design with the use of a self-structured questionnaire as an instrument for data collection. The sample size for the study was 63, and 52 copies of the questionnaire designed for this were retrieved and found useful for the study; hence return rate is 82%. This study revealed that entrepreneurship skills possessed by information professionals in Lagos State are printing information resources, publishing, and bindery and photocopying with a mean value of 3.67. The study further established that Competitive Intelligence (CI) strategies utilised by information professionals in Lagos State libraries

were on delivering products and services, with a mean of 3.19 CI strategies demonstrating positive contributions to the institution's mission, objectives, and goals. The study recommends that librarians and information professionals should endeavour to engage in research on how to acquire relevant CI on promoting the profession and to enable them to contribute meaningfully to the development of their organisation. The study also recommend that librarians and information professionals should increase their entrepreneurial skills to establish more services that can be of benefit to the users and parent institution. These can also serve as revenue generation to the institution such as establishing a publishing firm, information broker unit in the library.

Keywords: Competitive Intelligence, Entrepreneurship Skills, Marketing, Library Services, Librarians.

Introduction

The library plays a pivotal role in communities by providing access to information resources and services that enrich and empower individuals. The rapid growth in technology has drastically changed and transformed the way and manner in which library and information products and services are offered and as well put the libraries at the centre of hyper-competition. For libraries to survive the trend of competition there is a need for effective marketing strategies to reach and engage with the users. Library and information centres have begun to realise that by using marketing principles and techniques, they

can better understand their users' information needs. In recent years libraries have embraced marketing strategies to connect with users. Libraries now create and engage content utilisation targeting advertising which enables the library to effectively reach a wider audience and increase awareness of services rendered.

Cheng et al. (2020) stated that the library now markets its service on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp to engage with patrons and promote services. Libraries now involve in a various marketing strategies in order to showcase their resources and provide relevant services that will meet users' information needs. Smith et al. (2020) found that libraries are now engaged in creating blog posts, videos and podcasts to share information and promote service delivery. Providing valuable and relevant content will enhance better patronage in the community. Hence, marketing library services is essential for the library to remain relevant and engaged with the communities by providing relevant entrepreneurial skills and value which leads to the growth and development of the users. Marketing library services involves entrepreneurial skills which aim at creating better awareness and more value for the library through services rendered, as the users can easily enjoy satisfaction in meeting their information needs. The library now modernises its services by engaging entrepreneurship skills in order to promote service delivery that will be effective in this technological era. The libraries are now evolving into dynamic community hubs, offering more than just books. Libraries are now involved in becoming spaces that foster innovation, creativity, and entrepreneurship services to their users. Libraries have long been champions of education and lifelong learning, and their role in supporting entrepreneurship is a natural extension of this mission.

Awurdi and Mohammed (2018) viewed entrepreneurship as a major source of survival in the unemployment challenges faced by global economic and financial crises in the nation. The libraries support entrepreneurship by offering infopreneurs services and access to business in the environment. This includes business databases, market research reports, and business planning software. By providing these resources, libraries empower entrepreneurs to conduct thorough research. Furthermore, libraries are increasingly partnering with local organisations and businesses to support entrepreneurship. This can include co-hosting events, offering mentorship programmes, and providing access to funding opportunities. A

priro study revealed that libraries that actively engage with the local entrepreneurship ecosystem are able to better support aspiring entrepreneurs and contribute to economic growth. The libraries play a crucial role in fostering entrepreneurship skills and supporting aspiring entrepreneurs. By offering access to resources, training programmes, and partnerships, libraries empower individuals to pursue their entrepreneurial dreams and contribute to their communities. the role of libraries continues to evolve, their impact on entrepreneurship is expected to grow, making them valuable allies in the journey of entrepreneurs.

Cox (2018) submits that institutional leadership no longer perceive the library as the heart of the campus due to the availability of other sources of academic and research information, hence the library needs to represent their services and redeem their images in the institution. Jamaludin et al. (2014) stated that users are the reason why libraries exist therefore marketing the library services is essentially for meeting the information needs of the users. Therefore, for effective marketing of services and products of the library, it is essential to involve competitive intelligence (CI) to enable the studying of the environment and various entrepreneurship opportunities therein.

Entrepreneurship skills refer to the specific set of abilities and competencies that individuals need to create, manage, and grow a successful business. These skills are essential for identifying business opportunities, mobilising resources, and driving innovation. Having the right entrepreneurship skills are importance such as opportunity recognition, innovation and creativity, strategic planning, financial management skills, and leadership and team management skills

Opportunity recognition is a foundational entrepreneurship skill, involving the ability to identify viable business opportunities. Chavoushi et al. (2021), entrepreneurs who excel in opportunity recognition often demonstrate a higher degree of alertness to changes in the market environment. This skill is crucial for initiating and sustaining successful entrepreneurial ventures. Innovation and Creativity: are essential for entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurs must continuously generate new ideas and solutions to stay competitive. Innovation is not only about creating new products or services but also about improving processes and business models. Their study emphasises the role of creative thinking and problem-solving in driving business growth. Strategic planning involves setting long-term goals and defining

the actions needed to achieve them. Mohammad et al. (2024) indicate that effective strategic planning helps entrepreneurs navigate uncertainties and adapt to changing market conditions. The ability to develop and implement strategic plans is linked to sustained business success and growth. Financial management skills are crucial for managing resources and ensuring the financial health of a business. Bai (2023), proficient financial management involves budgeting, financial analysis, and securing funding. Their research suggests that entrepreneurs who possess strong financial management skills are better equipped to manage risks and capitalise on opportunities. Leadership and team management skills are critical for guiding and motivating teams. Vu (2020) emphasises that effective leadership involves not only directing but also inspiring and empowering employees. Good leadership fosters a positive work environment and enhances overall business performance.

Olayemi et al. (2022) viewed competitive intelligence as a systematic process and innovative way to generate competitive advantage for entrepreneurs. Haliso and Aina (2012) opined that competitive intelligence is an important tool that can assist entrepreneurs in making the right decisions than their competitors. Accordingly, information entrepreneurs can inculcate competitive intelligence process by collecting data on both their competitors and the external environment, which will enable the business to have better edge over its competitors. Competitive intelligence refers to the ability to gather, analyse, and use information collected on competitors, customers, and other market factors that contribute to a business's competitive advantage (Iwu-James et al., 2020). Competitive intelligence helps retain and satisfy customers by revealing the strategies and tactics of competitors, the competitors' level of control or share of the market, their strengths, weaknesses, and the combined effect of all the aforementioned on the library. In today's unpredictable economy, the application of CI to the marketing of library services is a proactive technique for creating value and sustaining the future. Competitive intelligence is important because it helps businesses (such as libraries) understand their competitive environment and the opportunities and challenges it presents. Businesses analyse the information to create effective and efficient practices, therefore the library needs these skills to understand various competitors and grant the library the upper hand over another information

provider. In today's impulsive economy, the application of CI to the marketing of library services is a proactive technique for creating value and sustaining the future. Bhardwaj and Jain (2016) also described the need to adopt marketing of library resources and services as; promotion of resources; user awareness; Improving the library's reputation; and marketing the services to generate corpus.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing competition among information service providers, including commercial digital platforms and institutional repositories, has necessitated the adoption of strategic marketing approaches by academic librarians to ensure the visibility and utilisation of library services. University libraries are expected to provide innovative and user-centred services, yet many remain underutilised due to inadequate marketing strategies. This underutilisation raises concerns about the effectiveness of librarians in promoting their services and highlights the need to examine the factors influencing their marketing efforts.

Competitive intelligence, which involves gathering and analysing information about competitors, market trends, and user preferences, has been recognised as a crucial factor in business and organisational success (Maluleka and Chummun, 2023). In the library context, the ability of librarians to apply competitive intelligence can enhance their strategic decision-making, improve service delivery, and attract more users (Adesina et al., 2022). However, little empirical research has been conducted on the extent to which competitive intelligence skills influence the marketing of library services in Nigerian academic institutions.

Similarly, entrepreneurship skills including innovation, risk-taking, and proactive engagement with library users are critical in transforming traditional library operations into dynamic and demand-driven services (Iroaganachi, 2022). Entrepreneurship in librarianship fosters the development of new services, revenue-generating activities, and sustainable marketing strategies. Despite the increasing emphasis on entrepreneurial approaches in library management, there remains a gap in understanding how entrepreneurship skills correlate with marketing effectiveness among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities. Given the growing demand for library services to remain competitive and relevant, this study seeks to examine how libraries could imbibe competitive

intelligence, entrepreneurship skills, and the marketing of library services among academic librarians.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the influence of entrepreneurship skills and competitive intelligence as tools for marketing library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What entrepreneurship skills are possessed as an information professional in Lagos State, Nigeria
2. What entrepreneurship skills do you utilise as an information professional for marketing library services in Lagos state, Nigeria?
3. What competitive intelligence strategies do you utilise as an information professional in Lagos State libraries
4. What CI techniques have you utilised as a librarian in marketing library services in Lagos State libraries?
5. What strategies do librarians use in marketing library services in Lagos State libraries

Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between competitive intelligence and marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between entrepreneurship skills and marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities

Ho3: Competitive intelligence and entrepreneurship skills jointly have no significant relationship on the marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities

Methodology

The research design for this study was a descriptive survey. This design was chosen because it allows the researcher to gather data that is statistically easy to analyse. The study used a self-structured questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire was developed by the researchers with

guidance from existing literature. The instrument's face, content, and construct validity were utilised, with the structured questionnaire reviewed by experts in the field of library science for assessment. The questionnaire was administered to respondents in various institutions through research assistance. The study population included librarians from state and federal universities in Lagos State, specifically: Lagos State University (LASU) with 23 librarians, Lagos State University of Education (LASUED) in Otto/Ijanikin with 8 librarians, Lagos State University of Technology (LASUTECH) in Ikorodu with 7 librarians, and the University of Lagos (UNILAG) in Akoka with 24 librarians, making a total of 63 professional librarians. Due to the small size of the population, the entire population was utilised for the study. A simple random sampling technique was employed to distribute the questionnaires across the universities. The data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software, and the results are presented accordingly. This study was carried out in 2024.

Results and Discussion of Findings

An analysis of the study response rate was carried out. The response rate of the study was calculated to determine the actual number of participants who took part in the study. The study administered sixty-three (63) copies of the questionnaire. Out of these, fifty-two copies were duly completed and returned making them suitable for analysis. This represents a response rate of 82%. The data were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software. The structure of this analysis followed demographic information of respondents and research questions.

Table 1 provides a detailed overview of the demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study. Demographic factors play a critical role in shaping the entrepreneurial and competitive intelligence capabilities of academic librarians. Understanding these dynamics is essential for designing targeted training programmes, fostering innovation, and enhancing marketing strategies in public university libraries. This study indicates that demographic factors such as gender, age, marital status, educational qualification, and years of experience significantly impact competitive intelligence and entrepreneurship skills among academic librarians. These factors influence how

librarians acquire, apply, and leverage these skills in marketing library services effectively. This study sample indicates a slightly higher representation of male librarians (53.85%) compared to female librarians (46.15%). While both genders demonstrate entrepreneurial competencies and competitive intelligence, studies suggest that gender-based differences may influence risk-taking behaviour, innovation, and adaptability in marketing library services. Male librarians exhibit a higher inclination toward strategic risk-taking, while female librarians. The age distribution indicates that the majority (38.46%) of librarians fall within the 41-50 age range, followed by 23.08% in both the 31-40 and

51-60 age groups. Younger librarians (20-30 years, 11.54%) exhibit greater adaptability to technological advancements and innovative marketing techniques, including digital and social media platforms. Conversely, older librarians (51 years and above) rely more on traditional competitive intelligence strategies, drawing from experience and established professional networks to market library services effectively. Dijk and Smidts (2021) supported the findings of this study through their survey on gender differences in risk assessment conducted at Cambridge University, United Kingdom. Their results indicated that there was no significant difference between genders in their tendency to take social risks.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents.

		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	28	53.85
	Female	24	46.15
	Total	52	100.00
Age	20-30	6	11.54
	31-40	12	23.08
	41-50	20	38.46
	51-60	12	23.08
	61 and above	2	3.85
	Total	52	100.00
Marital status	Single	30	57.69
	Married	10	19.23
	Divorced	6	11.54
	Widow/Widower	6	11.54
	Total	52	100.00
Level of Education	Degree	17	32.69
	Master's Degree	26	50.00
	PHD	8	15.38
	Others	1	1.92
	Total	52	100.00
Year of Experience	0-10	17	32.70
	11-20	25	48.08
	21-30	6	11.53
	31 and above	4	7.69
	Total	52	100

The data show that a majority (57.69%) of respondents are single, followed by married (19.23%) and divorced/widowed individuals (19.23%). Marital status may influence entrepreneurial risk-taking and decision-making, with single librarians potentially having more flexibility and willingness to explore new marketing strategies. Married librarians, on the other hand, may prioritise stable and risk-mitigated approaches in implementing competitive intelligence strategies. Educational attainment is a crucial factor in shaping entrepreneurship skills and competitive intelligence. The findings reveal that 50.00% of

respondents possess a master's degree, 32.69% hold a bachelor's degree, and 15.38% have a PhD. Advanced degrees likely contribute to higher competency levels in business acumen, data-driven decision-making, and strategic marketing techniques. Librarians with postgraduate qualifications have a deeper understanding of market trends, customer engagement strategies, and service innovation, thereby enhancing marketing effectiveness. The majority of respondents (48.08%) have 11-20 years of experience, followed by 32.70% with 0-10 years. Work experience significantly impacts how librarians apply competitive intelligence

in assessing user needs, identifying competitors, and positioning library services effectively.

Possessed by Information Professionals in Lagos State, Nigeria (SA=4; A=3; D=2; SD=1)

Table 2 identifies the Entrepreneurship Skills

Table 2: Entrepreneurship Skills Possessed by Information Professionals N=52.

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean SD
Entrepreneurship Skills					
I have entrepreneurial skills in printing information resources	0 .00%	2 3.85%	13 25.00%	37 71.15%	3.67 .55
I have entrepreneurial skills in publishing	0 .00%	6 11.54%	8 15.38%	38 73.08%	3.62 .69
Printing and publishing have enhanced entrepreneurial skills in my library	0 .00%	4 7.69%	39 75.00%	9 17.31%	3.10 .50
Bindery and Photocopying					
My entrepreneurial skills in bindery have enhanced my library marketing services to users	0 .00%	5 9.62%	36 69.23%	11 21.15%	3.12 .55
Entrepreneurial skills possessed by me in photocopying have promoted marketing library services	0 .00%	4 7.69%	38 73.08%	10 19.23%	3.12 .51
Bindery and photocopying promote library services by enhancing users' access to the resources	0 .00%	14 26.92%	26 50.00%	12 23.08%	2.96 .71
Information Brokerage and Consultancy Services					
I have entrepreneurial skills to provide information brokerage to users in the library	0 .00%	10 19.23%	30 57.69%	12 23.08%	3.04 .66
I have entrepreneurial skills to render consultancy services to users in my library	0 .00%	14 26.92%	29 55.77%	9 17.31%	2.90 .66
My library provides consulting services which promote library images in the community	0 .00%	7 13.46%	37 71.15%	8 15.38%	3.02 .54
Operation of a Business Centre and Cyber Café Business					
I have the skills to operate business centres and it has improved my service delivery in the library	0 .00%	11 21.15%	29 55.77%	12 23.08%	3.02 .67
With the aid of technology, I can help the library establish cyber café businesses	0 .00%	9 17.31%	29 55.77%	14 26.92%	3.10 .66
The skills acquired in business centres have had a positive influence on my marketing relationship with users in the library	0 .00%	0 .00%	39 75.00%	13 25.00%	3.25 .44
Development of computer software					
I have enhanced the library in my software and hardware installation services business	0 .00%	3 5.77%	35 67.31%	14 26.92%	3.21 .54
With the help of entrepreneurial skills, I can develop computer software to promote service delivery in the library	2 3.85%	0 .00%	39 75.00%	11 21.15%	3.13 .60
With the aid of a computer, I can develop software that is more user-friendly	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	41 78.85%	5 9.62%	2.94 .57
Book Vendor Business					
Entrepreneurial skills enable me to provide book vendor services business to the library	2 3.85%	3 5.77%	35 67.31%	12 23.08%	3.10 .66
I provide library marketing business through newspaper vendor business	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	36 69.23%	12 23.08%	3.12 .65
I provide marketing strategies through these marketing books	1 1.92%	2 3.85%	37 71.15%	12 23.08%	3.15 .57
Average Mean	3.09 0.24				

Table 2 illustrates the entrepreneurship skills possessed by information professionals in Lagos State, Nigeria, providing insights into their perceived capabilities in various entrepreneurial endeavours within library settings.

i. **Printing Information Resources:** Information professionals demonstrate a strong entrepreneurial aptitude in printing information resources, with a

mean of 3.67. The majority strongly agree (71.15%) that they possess skills in this area, indicating a high proficiency in leveraging printing for information dissemination.

- ii. **Publishing:** Professionals exhibit significant entrepreneurial skills in publishing, with a mean of 3.62.
- iii. **Information Brokerage and Consultancy Services:** Professionals express considerable

entrepreneurial skills in information brokerage and consultancy services, with means of 3.04 and 2.90, respectively. A substantial majority (57.69% and 55.77%, respectively) acknowledge possessing these skills, indicating their capacity to provide specialised services to library users.

- iv. Operation of Business Centres and Cyber Café Businesses: Skills in operating business centres and cyber café businesses are well-established, with means of 3.02 and 3.10, respectively.
- v. Book Vendor Business: Entrepreneurial skills in book vendor businesses are evident, with means ranging from 3.10 to 3.15.

Professionals strongly agree on their ability to provide these services, indicating their role in marketing library resources effectively. Overall, the average mean across all items is 3.09, with a standard deviation of 0.24. This suggests a consistent perception among information professionals of their entrepreneurship skills in various facets of library management. It reflects a strong entrepreneurial spirit and adaptability within the profession, with professionals adept at utilising

diverse strategies to enhance library services and outreach in Lagos State, Nigeria.

This study supports the prior literature. Leadership in academic libraries: A case study of innovative leadership practices. They established that librarians possess a range of entrepreneurial skills that enable them to adapt to changing environments, meet user's needs and drive innovation in library services. Olayemi et al. (2022) who examined information-driven entrepreneurship affirm that entrepreneurship enhances the creation of employment opportunities, it also provides librarians with a broad understanding and exposure to how to start and run a business venture in the area of their choosing career. However, Makinde et al. (2023) negate the findings that assess the entrepreneurial skills level of librarians, revealing lacklustre technical, business and ICT skills of librarians and information professionals

Table 3 examines entrepreneurship skills utilised by information professionals for marketing library services in Lagos state, Nigeria (SA=4; A=3; D=2 SD=1)

Table 3: Entrepreneurship Skills Employed By Information Professional for Marketing Library Services N=52.

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean SD
Marketing	0 0.00%	3 5.77%	36 69.23%	13 25.00%	3.19 .53
Bindery	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	39 75.00%	9 17.31%	3.08 .55
Photocopying	0 0.00%	1 1.92%	39 75.00%	12 23.08%	3.21 .46
Publishing	3 5.77%	4 7.69%	36 69.23%	9 17.31%	2.98 .70
Information brokerage	0 0.00%	13 25.00%	27 51.92%	12 23.08%	2.98 .70
Operation of business centre and cybercafé business	2 3.85%	5 9.62%	32 61.54%	13 25.00%	3.08 .71
Development of computer software	0 0.00%	13 25.00%	27 51.92%	12 23.08%	2.98 .70
Book selling business	0 0.00%	14 26.92%	29 55.77%	9 17.31%	2.90 .66
Information consultancy services	0 0.00%	6 11.54%	37 71.15%	9 17.31%	3.06 .54
Online database and library software provision	3 5.77%	13 25.00%	25 48.08%	11 21.15%	2.85 .83
Average Mean			3.00	0.18	

Table 3 presents an examination of entrepreneurship skills utilised by information professionals for marketing library services in Lagos State, Nigeria, offering insights into their effectiveness in leveraging various strategies to promote library resources and engage users.

- i. Marketing: Information professionals exhibit a strong utilisation of marketing skills, with a mean of 3.19. While there's a significant agreement (69.23%) on their effectiveness in marketing, a notable portion also expresses some disagreement (25.00%), suggesting potential areas for improvement or

- differing perceptions among professionals.
- ii. Bindery/ Publishing: Utilisation of publishing services for marketing shows a mean of 2.98. While there’s agreement (69.23%) on their effectiveness, some express disagreement (17.31%), suggesting differing views on the impact of publishing activities in marketing library services.
- iii. Development of Computer Software: Utilisation of computer software development for marketing shows a mean of 2.98. While there’s agreement (51.92%) on their effectiveness, some express disagreement (23.08%), indicating potential areas for improvement or differing perceptions among professionals.
- iv. Information Consultancy Services: Utilisation of information consultancy services for marketing shows a mean of 3.06. While there’s agreement (71.15%) on their effectiveness, some express disagreement (17.31%), indicating potential areas for improvement or differing perceptions among professionals.
- v. Online Database and Library Software Provision:
This suggests a moderate level of agreement

among information professionals regarding the effectiveness of entrepreneurship skills in marketing library services in Lagos State, Nigeria. However, there are areas where opinions vary, indicating the need for further exploration and potentially targeted interventions to enhance marketing strategies within library contexts. This study Sharma and Pathak (2020) affirms who established that the effective use of various marketing tools and techniques can considerably enhance the effectiveness of promoting library services and products. The study further indicated that entrepreneurship skills are essential for information professionals to effectively market libraries attract users, and promote the value of librarians in their communities. In the same vein, Komolafe-Opadeji and Haliso (2012) affirm that libraries adopt various marketing strategies to enhance the effectiveness and promote library services to their users.

Table 4: identifies competitive intelligence (CI) strategies utilised by information professionals in Lagos State libraries (SA=4; A=3; D=2; SD= 1)

Table 4: Identification of Competitive Intelligence (CI) Strategies (N=52).

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean SD
Product and Services					
CI has enabled me to deliver products and services targeted at meeting the information requirements of the users	2 3.85%	8 15.38%	30 57.69%	12 23.08%	3.00 .74
CI has enabled me to be creative and innovative through product differentiation and flexibility to design, customise, and package for users in the library	0 0.00%	9 17.31%	32 61.54%	11 21.15%	3.04 .63
CI has influenced service delivery and planning resulting in more productivity on the users’ end.	2 3.85%	12 23.08%	32 61.54%	6 11.54%	2.81 .69
Price					
CI has enabled me to demonstrate positive contributions to the institution’s mission, objectives and goal	2 3.85%	10 19.23%	30 57.69%	10 19.23%	2.92 .74
CI has enable my library to have quality value in the sight of the parent institution	2 3.85%	8 15.38%	36 69.23%	6 11.54%	2.88 .65
Place					
CI has enhance good interaction between the library and the parent institution	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	34 65.38%	10 19.23%	3.00 .69
CI has help my library to meet the actual needs of the users and this has enhance service delivery	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	34 65.38%	12 23.08%	3.08 .68
CI has enable my library to add value to the library hence receiving favour in request for institutional development	2 3.85%	8 15.38%	36 69.23%	6 11.54%	2.88 .65
People					
I assist my library to provide quick service delivery which enhances users to utilising library services	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	30 57.69%	14 26.92%	3.08 .74
CI helps to provide excellent marketing service that results in a value for users	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	30 57.69%	14 26.92%	3.08 .74
CI enhances my technological interest in developing marketing services that will satisfy present user needs	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	30 57.69%	14 26.92%	3.08 .74
Process					
I promote easy access to information resources and it has influence users interest on the library	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	34 65.38%	12 23.08%	3.08 .68
My library employs highly digital tools to promote the process of library marketing delivery	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	36 69.23%	12 23.08%	3.12 .65

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean SD
My library employs automated tools to enhance quick service delivery to users in the library	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	42 80.77%	6 11.54%	3.00 .56
Promotion					
I promote library awareness to users on social handles such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and it has influenced the positive users turn out in my academic library	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	40 76.92%	8 15.38%	3.04 .59
I promote library marketing through SDI to users through emails and social media	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	38 73.08%	8 15.38%	3.00 .63
I promote marketing library services to various social media groups in my institution	3 5.77%	1 1.92%	40 76.92%	8 15.38%	3.02 .64
Physical Evidence					
My library has a modern physical structure that will motivate users in utilising the services	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	30 57.69%	14 26.92%	3.08 .74
My library is well equipped which \motivates users to utilise the services	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	34 65.38%	10 19.23%	3.00 .69
The conducive environment in my library serves as a marketing strategy which results to more users	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	32 61.54%	14 26.92%	3.12 .70
Average Mean	3.03 0.08				

Table 5 identifies CI techniques utilised by State Libraries (SA=4; A=3; D=2; SD=1) librarians in marketing library services in Lagos

Table 5: Techniques in Marketing Library Services (N=52).

Technological Intelligence Techniques	SA	A	D	SD	Mean SD
I process CI skills to access relevant information which can enable me to have better library marketing services	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	40 76.92%	8 15.38%	3.06 .54
I know technicalities to harness information that leads me to market library services	4 7.69%	4 7.69%	38 73.08%	6 11.54%	2.88 .70
My CI technical skills have increased library marketing in my institution	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	36 69.23%	12 23.08%	3.13 .60
Marketing Intelligence Techniques					
My library engages CI strategy which influences effective performance in photocopying unit	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	28 53.85%	16 30.77%	3.12 .76
My library employs CI strategies that increase good marketing revenue in bindery and printing	2 3.85%	6 11.54%	36 69.23%	8 15.38%	2.96 .66
My library involve CI strategy which improves effective performance in the publishing unit	2 3.85%	8 15.38%	32 61.54%	10 19.23%	2.96 .71
My library engage CI strategy in promoting various relevant services to the users	2 3.85%	8 15.38%	32 61.54%	10 19.23%	2.96 .71
Opportunities Intelligence Techniques					
My library utilises opportunities of CI strategies that improve the Strength of production	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	40 76.92%	8 15.38%	3.06 .54
My library engages CI strategies that reduce the Weakness in service provision in the library	4 7.69%	2 3.85%	36 69.23%	10 19.23%	3 .74
My library maximised available opportunities that boast services quality	3 5.77%	1 1.92%	42 80.77%	6 11.54%	2.98 .61
My library employs tactics that will reduce threats to the provision of services in the library	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	34 65.38%	12 23.08%	3.08 .68
Average Mean	3.02 0.16				

Table 5 delineates the competitive intelligence (CI) techniques utilized by librarians in marketing library services in Lagos State Libraries, showcasing the methods employed to gather, analyze, and utilize information for strategic marketing purposes. Also, for Technological Intelligence Techniques, Librarians leverage CI skills to access relevant information,

understand technicalities to harness information for marketing, and increase library marketing effectiveness. The mean for this section is 3.02., Similarly, in Marketing Intelligence Techniques, Libraries engage CI strategies to influence effective performance in units such as photocopying, bindery and printing, and publishing. Additionally, CI strategies are employed to

promote various relevant services to users. The mean for this section is 3.00. For, Opportunities Intelligence Techniques, Libraries utilize CI strategies to improve strengths in production, reduce weaknesses in service provision, maximize available opportunities to boost service quality, and employ tactics to reduce threats in service provision. The mean for this section is 3.06. Overall, the average mean across all sections is 3.02, with a standard deviation of 0.16.

This indicates a consistent perception among librarians regarding the effectiveness of Competitive Intelligence techniques in marketing library services in Lagos State Libraries. This study Makinde et al. (2023) supports who established that CI techniques help librarians gather and analyze relevant information,

understand user needs and preferences, and develop targeted marketing strategies to promote library services effectively. Makinde et al. (2023) further indicated the following CI techniques utilized by librarians in marketing library services: competitor analysis, social media monitoring, and user Surveys and Feedback. In vain, Panda and Kaur (2023) also affirmed that Librarians collect user feedback through surveys, suggestion boxes, and user reviews to gather insights into user preferences and expectations. This information is valuable for improving services and marketing initiatives.

Table 6: identifies strategies librarians use in marketing library services in Lagos State Libraries (SA=4; A=3; D=2; SD=1)

Table 6: Strategies used in Marketing Library Services (N=52).

	SA	A	D	SD	Mean SD
Use of social media (i.e. Facebook, MySpace, Twitter)	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	32 61.54%	16 30.77%	3.21 .64
To enlighten the users on the relevance of library use	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	34 65.38%	14 26.92%	3.15 .67
To enlighten the users on the relevance of library use	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	34 65.38%	14 26.92%	3.15 .67
Use of email	3 5.77%	1 1.92%	32 61.54%	16 30.77%	3.17 .73
Use of text messages	4 7.69%	8 15.38%	26 50.00%	14 26.92%	2.96 .86
Newsletter marketing	2 3.85%	4 7.69%	32 61.54%	14 26.92%	3.12 .70
Use of selective dissemination of Information (SDI)	3 5.77%	1 1.92%	34 65.38%	14 26.92%	3.13 .71
To improve interpersonal relationship between librarians and users	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	36 69.23%	12 23.08%	3.12 .65
Provision of electronic access to information	3 5.77%	1 1.92%	30 57.69%	18 34.62%	3.21 .75
Exhibitions and display of new arrivals	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	32 61.54%	16 30.77%	3.21 .64
Organizing user education	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	26 50.00%	22 42.31%	3.33 .68
Having representative in institutional functions	1 1.92%	3 5.77%	34 65.38%	14 26.92%	3.17 .62
Organizing and researching into indigenous knowledge in the community	2 3.85%	2 3.85%	36 69.23%	12 23.08%	3.12 .65
Average Mean			3.16	0.22	

Table 6 provides a comprehensive overview of the strategies employed by librarians in Lagos State Libraries to market library services. Across various avenues, librarians employ a diverse array of techniques to engage users and enhance the visibility and relevance of library resources. One prominent strategy is the utilization of social media platforms such as Facebook, MySpace, and Twitter. Through these channels, librarians disseminate information about library

services, events, and resources, effectively reaching out to a wide audience. This approach, with a mean score of 3.21, indicates its effectiveness in leveraging modern communication tools for library marketing efforts. Moreover, librarians actively undertake initiatives to enlighten users about the relevance and importance of utilizing library resources..

Librarians also employ newsletter marketing and selective dissemination of information (SDI)

as effective strategies to inform users about library offerings. By curating and delivering relevant content directly to users' inboxes or through targeted dissemination, librarians enhance user awareness and engagement. With a mean score of 3.21, this strategy underscores the importance of technological infrastructure in supporting modern library services and user needs. Additionally, librarians organize exhibitions and display new arrivals to attract user interest and promote awareness of available resources. By showcasing the latest additions to the collection, librarians enhance user engagement and encourage exploration of library offerings. This strategy, with a mean score of 3.21, reflects its effectiveness in capturing user attention and driving interest in library services. Librarians also play an active role in organising user education sessions to enhance information literacy skills and promote awareness of library resources. With a mean score of 3.33, this strategy highlights the commitment to empowering users with the knowledge and skills needed to maximize library resources effectively. Overall, the average mean score across all strategies is 3.16, with a standard deviation of 0.22.

This indicates a consistent perception among librarians regarding the effectiveness of various strategies in marketing library services in Lagos State Libraries. This study corroborates Smith et al. (2020) who revealed that librarians and informational professionals now engage in utilizing social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram to engage users and promote library events and resources. Camacho et al. (2020) also established that digital marketing techniques such as search engine optimisation (SEO) and content marketing are also utilized to increase the visibility of library services online. In the same vein, Yadukrishnan et al. (2023) established that librarians' collaboration with stakeholders is another effective strategy used to market library services. A prior study further highlighted the importance of collaborating with faculty, students, and community organisations to promote library resources and events

Analyses of Hypotheses

H₁: There is no significant relationship between competitive intelligence and marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities.

Table 7: Correlation Between Competitive Intelligence and Marketing of Library Services.

Correlations			
		Competitive Intelligence	Marketing of Library Services
Competitive Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	.947**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	52	52
Marketing of library services	Pearson Correlation	.947**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	52	52
Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

The correlational analysis conducted between competitive intelligence and marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities reveals a highly significant relationship between these two variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient of .947 indicates a strong positive correlation between competitive intelligence activities and the marketing efforts of library services. This suggests that as competitive intelligence practices increase within these academic libraries, there is a corresponding significant increase in the marketing activities aimed at promoting library services. The p-value of .000 further confirms this relationship, indicating that the likelihood of such a strong correlation occurring by random chance

is extremely low, thus reinforcing the robustness of the findings.

These results underscore the importance of competitive intelligence in shaping marketing strategies within academic libraries. Academic librarians in Lagos State public universities who engage in systematic competitive intelligence gathering are likely to leverage this knowledge to enhance their marketing initiatives effectively. By understanding competitors' strengths, weaknesses, and strategies, librarians can tailor their marketing efforts to better meet user needs and promote library services more strategically. This correlation highlights the symbiotic relationship between proactive intelligence gathering and effective marketing in the context of

academic libraries, emphasising the role of data-driven decision-making in optimising service delivery and user engagement. These findings align with previous research emphasising the role of competitive intelligence in strategic marketing and innovation within the library sector (Amaeshi and Okoye, 2021). Studies have also shown that academic librarians who employ competitive intelligence techniques, such as

environmental scanning and user analysis, are more likely to design tailored services that meet evolving information needs (Yadukrishnan et al., 2023).

H₂: There is no significant relationship between entrepreneurship skills and marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities.

Table 8: Correlation Between Entrepreneurship Skills and Marketing of Library Services.

Correlations			
		Entrepreneurial Skills	Marketing of Library Services
Entrepreneurial Skills	Pearson Correlation	1	.937**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	52	52
Marketing of library services	Pearson Correlation	.937**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	52	52

. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlational analysis between entrepreneurial skills and the marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities shows a strong and statistically significant relationship. The Pearson correlation coefficient of .937** suggests a very high positive correlation, indicating that as entrepreneurial skills among librarians increase, their ability to market library services also improves significantly. The p-value of .000 confirms the statistical significance of this relationship, meaning that the correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance and is highly reliable.

These findings highlight the crucial role of entrepreneurial skills in enhancing the marketing of library services. Librarians with strong entrepreneurial abilities are likely to be more innovative, proactive, and strategic in promoting library services to their target audience. This suggests that fostering entrepreneurial competencies among academic librarians can lead to

more effective marketing initiatives, helping libraries attract more users and improve service delivery. The strong correlation underscores the importance of integrating entrepreneurship training into librarianship to enhance the visibility and relevance of library services in academic institutions. This research supports previous findings, indicating that entrepreneurial librarianship fosters service expansion, user engagement, and increased library visibility (Doulani et al., 2020). Studies further suggest that when librarians possess entrepreneurial competencies, they can effectively design new service models, utilise digital platforms, and establish partnerships to market library services more dynamically (Makinde et al., 2023).

H₃: Competitive intelligence and entrepreneurship skills jointly have no significant relationship on the marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities.

Table 9: Correlation Between Competitive Intelligence and Entrepreneurship Skills and Marketing of Library Services.

Correlations				
		Competitive Intelligence	Marketing of Library Services	Entrepreneurial Skills
Competitive Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	.947**	.974**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	52	52	52
Marketing of library services	Pearson Correlation	.947**	1	.937**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	52	52	52
Entrepreneurial Skills	Pearson Correlation	.974**	.937**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	52	52	52

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlational analysis examining the joint relationship between competitive intelligence, entrepreneurial skills, and the marketing of library services among academic librarians in Lagos State public universities reveals a strong and significant connection among these variables. The Pearson correlation coefficients show that competitive intelligence has a high positive correlation with marketing of library services ($r = .947, p = .000$) and entrepreneurial skills ($r = .974, p = .000$). Similarly, entrepreneurial skills also demonstrate a strong correlation with marketing of library services ($r = .937, p = .000$). These findings indicate that both competitive intelligence and entrepreneurial skills are significantly and positively associated with the marketing of library services, suggesting that improvements in these skills contribute to enhanced marketing efforts.

The strength and significance of these correlations suggest that competitive intelligence and entrepreneurial skills jointly play a crucial role in shaping the marketing strategies of academic librarians. Since both variables exhibit a strong relationship with marketing, it is evident that librarians who effectively integrate competitive intelligence with entrepreneurial skills are better equipped to market their library services successfully. This implies that fostering both competencies among academic librarians could lead to more strategic, innovative, and user-focused marketing approaches. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_3), which posits no significant relationship between these variables and marketing, is not supported by the data, affirming that competitive intelligence and entrepreneurial skills are essential drivers of effective library service marketing. This result aligns with existing literature suggesting that entrepreneurial skills and competitive intelligence are complementary factors that drive strategic decision-making and innovation in service marketing (Špiranec, Zorica & Kos, 2023). Libraries that integrate market intelligence with entrepreneurial strategies are more likely to adapt to changing user expectations, leverage technological advancements, and create sustainable value for their patrons.

Conclusion

This study established the importance of marketing in librarianship. Librarianship is experiencing rapid change and many factors are reshaping the role of libraries, thus several things have compelled librarians and information professionals to learn about marketing their services to users. By acquiring and utilising effective entrepreneurship skills and competitive intelligence

skills, librarians and information professionals can enhance their services in their communities thereby promoting the beauty of the profession. This study revealed that entrepreneurship skills possessed by information professionals in Lagos State are printing information resources, publishing, and bindery and photocopying. The study further established that competitive intelligence (CI) strategies utilised by information professionals in Lagos state libraries were on delivering products and services, price, CI strategies demonstrate positive contributions to the institution's mission, objectives, and goals). The study further provides a comprehensive overview of the strategies employed by librarians in Lagos State libraries to market library services such as the utilisation of social media platforms such as Facebook, MySpace, and Twitter. This study established that there are significant correlations that suggest that librarians who engage in competitive intelligence gathering and possess entrepreneurial competencies are more effective in promoting library services. These findings underscore the need for professional training programmes, workshops, and institutional policies that equip librarians with these essential skills to enhance service delivery in academic libraries.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the finding of this study, the following recommendations are hereby made

1. The librarians and information professionals should endeavour to engage in research on how to acquire relevant CI on promoting the profession and to enable them to contribute meaningfully to the development of their organisation.
2. The librarians and information professionals should increase their entrepreneurial skills to establish more services that can be of benefit to the users and parent institutions. These can also serve as revenue generation to the institution such as establishing a publishing firm, information broker unit in the library
3. The library management should provide a conducive environment that will enable the librarians utilise their entrepreneurial skills in order to promote the library serves
4. The management should endeavour to send librarians and information professionals to relevant workshops and seminars that will enable them to acquire recent skills to promote services in their units

5. Academic institutions and library management invest in continuous professional development programmes focused on marketing, competitive intelligence, and entrepreneurship.
6. That libraries management should integrate digital marketing strategies and data-driven decision-making to enhance service delivery and user engagement.

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